

Report about EOSCpilot WP3 Ethics Survey

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All the experts answered individually and not on behalf of their own organisation

1. Summary

1.1 Introduction

The EOSCpilot project has recently published draft policy recommendations (Del 3.3) as a step towards establishing the required policy environment to support the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The inclusion of ethical principles and policies are of fundamental importance to the EOSC, but it is difficult to anticipate all the ethical issues that may emerge as the scientific, technical, social and political landscape evolves. Therefore, a survey was performed to collect feedback on the proposals made from the different key stakeholder groups, plus explore how the draft recommendations can be integrated into the 'policy supporting services' that now need to be developed.

1.2 Methods

An online questionnaire was developed, covering 14 questions referring to the ethics section of the draft policy recommendations, and implemented with the EUSurvey tool. The questionnaire was sent to 42 invited participants, representing the main EOSC stakeholder categories and selected from two groups: ethics experts already involved in the project and persons registered at the EOSCpilot webpage, who indicated interest in ethical questions and willingness to contribute. The online survey was launched on 27 August 2018 and closed on 29 September 2018. During the last two weeks the survey was publicly accessible and the link sent out through mailing lists and published on the EOSCpilot website. Five additional answers were therefore collected, for a total of 26 answers.

1.3 Results

21 out of 42 invited experts participated in the survey (response rate 50%). The majority of participants were from research producing organisations, academic institutions or research libraries (n=12), the rest was distributed to the other stakeholder categories. From the participants, 5 were ethics experts, 13 had some associations with ethics and 7 were interested in ethical questions, 1 participant chose other as an option.

The overwhelming majority (23/26) attested 'strongly' that supporting and promoting an ethical behaviour is of central importance to the EOSC and should be explicitly built into the organisation from the outset. With respect to supporting organisational ethics, the majority (19/26) did not have a 'strong' position and only 13/26 answered with 'yes'. Taken all comments together, two thirds of the participants were, however, in favour of minimal standards or a common ethical framework for EOSC and a small subgroup for ethical oversight.

There was a majority in favour of establishing additional mechanisms to support research integrity by EOSC (n=20). Two approaches were discussed, a) developing high level agreements/minimum/standards/ framework/ethical principles within EOSC and b) rely on existing mechanisms but extend or adapt if necessary. Despite high agreement that EOSC should work towards a uniform application of metadata standards (21/26), the answer pattern shows that the formulation of the question was not clear to all participants and challenges with respect to implementation were seen by several participants.

No clear answer pattern was observed with respect to monitoring and managing data aggregation to prevent unforeseen results: 18 participants agreed, 8 disagreed. Several participants were not happy with the formulation and direction of the question. The majority of participants (20/25) felt that the EOSC should try to introduce uniform policies with respect to the collection, storage, access and re-use of sensitive personal data; however, some criticism was raised, particularly by a substantial subgroup who suggested to work within the existing regulatory framework.

All participants (24/26) were in favour of time-limited expert working groups within the EOSC to consider specific legal and ethical issues and to propose relevant policies. Several proposals were made the way the work of these groups could be optimised. There was overwhelming agreement (24/26) with the concept of an independent EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board. Practical issues were raised about the composition and mandate of the board and the relation between the board and the EOSC management structure. The majority of participants (23/26) agreed that a periodic assessment of EOSC activities from the viewpoint of legal and ethical compliance makes sense and that the report should be public; however, a substantial subgroup raised diverse concerns regarding among others time and resources needed.

A need for training material and programmes to ensure understanding of ethical issues within the EOSC was expressed by the majority of participants (20/26). Answers to whether the EOSC should play an active role in wider debates promoting the interpretation of accurate scientific knowledge in society, revealed no clear pattern (yes: 13/26). A considerable group (n=8) brought up additional ethical issues to be discussed.

2. Background

The EOSCpilot project has recently published draft policy recommendations¹ as a step towards establishing the required policy environment to support the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (1). The inclusion of ethical principles and policies are of fundamental importance to the EOSC, but it is difficult to anticipate all the ethical issues that may emerge as the scientific, technical, social and political landscape evolves. It is therefore crucial to have governance mechanisms in place that can ensure ethical issues are appropriately dealt with in the future, irrespective of how and when they occur, as well as identifying and proposing responses to current issues. The complexity and diversity of potential issues requires an analysis of ethical issues relating to organisational conduct and policies, research conduct, research decision making, the use of data - especially sensitive data- and the interaction between science and society. Because of this complexity, the paper proposes that ethical issues can be managed at a variety of different 'layers' of involvement and commitment. It proposes that as a minimum:

- EOSC as an organisation should commit to act, and be seen to act, in an ethical manner, with policies and processes that reflect that commitment;
- EOSC should have structural mechanisms in place to support research integrity, for instance by establishing metadata systems that ensure accurate provenance data and appropriate acknowledgement of previous work.

Many other issues will need specialist ethical (and often legal) expertise, in time limited working groups, to propose specific policy responses. The paper's authors strongly support the use of such groups, but also strongly recommend the establishment of a coordinating body, an Ethical and Legal Advisory Board, to oversee the work of specialist working groups, and to monitor and report on the ethical practice of the organisation. Such a board would be distinct from the EOSC executive and be drawn from ethical and legal experts from stakeholder communities. The paper's authors believe EOSC also has an important role to play in raising awareness about ethical issues within scientific communities, as well as in wider ethical debates, for instance around the interplay of scientific knowledge and society. Such input could be introduced as the EOSC itself matures, and the level of available resources becomes clearer.

It was decided to seek feedback to the draft policy recommendations to formulate a set of final policy recommendations for publication in January 2019. The aim of the survey is to collect feedback on these

¹ <https://eoscipilot.eu/content/d33-Draft-Policy-Recommendations>

proposals from different key stakeholder groups, such as funders and ministries, research infrastructures (RIs), and research producing organisations (RPOs), plus explore how the recommendations above can be integrated into the 'policy supporting services' that now need to be developed.

3. Methods

A questionnaire was developed based upon the content of the EOSCpilot project Deliverable D3.3 (1) within Task 3.1.4 on ethics (see Appendix 1). The questionnaire covers 14 questions from the following areas:

- 1) Ethics issues, supporting organisational ethics and research integrity (Q3-Q6)
- 2) Use of data, personal and sensitive data (Q7-Q8)
- 3) The role of working groups and Ethics and Legal Advisory Board (Q9-Q11)
- 4) Training, Science and society, other issues (Q12-Q14)

For questions 3 to 11 participants were asked to express their agreement ('yes, strongly', 'yes, partially', 'no, strongly', 'no partially'), and a compulsory text for explanation was requested. For questions 12 to 14 participants were consulted on broader topics with an optional comment.

The questionnaire was implemented in the EUSurvey, an online survey management system for creating and publishing forms available to the public or dedicated recipients (2).

The questionnaire was sent to invited participants selected in order to cover the main EOSC stakeholder categories. Some of them were identified as ethics experts (few of them were already involved in the preparation of the draft guidelines or ethics experts proposed by WP3 of EOSCpilot), whilst others were selected from the list of persons registered at the EOSCpilot Webpage, who indicated interest in ethical questions and willingness to contribute (attending a workshop and/or review documents).

The online survey was launched on 27 August 2018 and send out to 42 invited participants. It was closed on 29 September 2018. In order to collect further contributions and cover stakeholder categories potentially less represented, it was decided to open the survey to a larger public during the last two weeks of September: the link to participate was sent out through mailing lists and published on the EOSCpilot website; during this period 5 additional anonymous answers were received.. All the figures presented in this report show the distribution of answers between the 'invited' survey and the 'open' survey.

4. Results

4.1 General information and ethics background

General information

21 out of 42 invited experts participated in the survey (response rate 50%), and 5 additional persons participated once the survey was publicly accessible, for a total of **26** answers. The majority of participants were from research producing organisations, academic institutions or research libraries (n=12), the rest was fairly distributed to research infrastructures (n=3), E-infrastructures, VREs or other pertinent H2020 projects (n=3), Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations (n=2), General public (n=2), Government ministries or agencies (n=2), Research funding bodies (n=1) and service providers (n=1).

Figure 1: *Number of participants per EOSCpilot stakeholder category*

Ethics background

To validate the robustness of the results the ethics background of the responders was identified (figure 2): 7 out of 26 responders defined themselves as experts in ethics.

Figure 2: Q1: Ethics background of the participants

4.2 Overall results

1. Ethics issues, supporting organisational ethics and research integrity

Q3: The importance of ethical issues

In figure 3 the distribution of answers to question 3 is presented:

Figure 3: Q3: The recommendations on ethics are based on the assumption that supporting and promoting ethical behaviour is of central importance to EOSC and should be explicitly built into the organisation from the outset. Do you agree with this assumption?

All participants answered 'yes' to this question. The overwhelming majority (23/26) attested 'strongly' that supporting and promoting an ethical behaviour is of central importance to EOSC and should be explicitly built into the organisation from the outset.

Reasons for stressing the importance of ethics are the risks associated with EOSC and open science, the need for trust, justification, research integrity and protecting moral values. The need for dealing with ethical aspects from the outset and at all stages of the EOSC was explicitly addressed by two experts. Issues related with personal/sensitive data were mentioned by four experts.

Q4: Supporting organisational ethics

In Figure 4 the results for question 4 are presented:

Figure 4: *Q4: EOSC will be a federation of different organisations, each with their own ethical practices and obligations, reflecting their own regulatory environments and the activities in which they are engaged. Do you think that this will be sufficient to ensure that EOSC, as a whole, acts as an ‘ethical organisation’?*

Here the answer pattern is not so clear. The overwhelming majority (19/26) did not have a ‘strong’ position. Fourteen experts indicated that to ensure that EOSC as a whole acts as an ethical organisation, it will be sufficient that the different organisations federated in EOSC have their own ethical practices and obligations; however, only three expert from this group ‘strongly’ supported this position. Twelve experts answered ‘no’, but only a minority gave a strong answer (n=4).

From the three participants who ‘strongly’ agreed, one mentioned transparency and scientific credit as important elements of open science and another stated that individual ethical principles and values have to respect general principles that are fundamental for the whole society.

The ‘yes, partially’ answers (n=11) cover a broader spectrum. Some are supportive of developing a common framework or common principles for EOSC (n=5) or are in favour of an oversight function (n=2). One expert favoured a partnership model with ethical experts, one saw new ethical challenges that might not be covered by existing regulations and one remarked that the EOSC’s own ethical practices, obligations and regulations should be coherent and address any differences among each organisation. Again the critical issue of sensitive data was mentioned (n=1).

From the ‘no, partially’ answers (n=8), all were in favour of minimal standards, ethical rules, a common framework or a set of principles for the EOSC.

From the four participants who strongly disagreed, two referred to the problem of individual standards of each institution or country, which may interfere with the whole ethical issues management and the others recommended to have a core set of principles.

Taken together all comments, two thirds of the participants were in favour of minimal standards or a common ethical framework for EOSC and a small subgroup for ethical oversight.

Q5: Supporting research integrity #1

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the answers to question 5:

Figure 5: *Q5: Research integrity (ethical principles relating to the good practice of the individual researcher) is currently supported by research review mechanisms and codes of conduct. Should EOSC establish additional review mechanisms and codes of conduct relating to the use of EOSC resources?*

The majority of survey participants was in favour of establishing additional mechanisms to support research integrity by the EOSC (n=20), however, only 9/20 ‘strongly’ agreed. From those who disagreed (n=6), three did it strongly.

In the ‘strong’ agreement group (n=9), a need for high level agreements, an ethical framework, minimum standards and ethical principles was expressed by 7 participants. This was underlined by one expert stating that relying on external mechanisms is insufficient. One participant stated that patient organisations need to be involved, which is certainly an important point.

From those, who ‘partially’ agreed (n=11), one opted for a pan-European code of conduct and 5 on an approach relying on what is already existing but with the option to extend and to adapt some principles/mechanisms/code of conduct. One participant remarked that support/check could be useful, another that a code of conduct should be included in institutional ethical guidelines. One participant argued that end users understanding of how the EOSC operates is necessary for the discussion. There was a further comment related to the use of metadata standards and a further one arguing that a broader perspective is needed taking exploitation of research into consideration.

Those who ‘partially’ disagreed (n=3) pointed out that unnecessary duplication should be avoided and existing codes should be supported. One statement referred to the point that research is not the focus of the EOOSC but rather supporting research.

From those participants who ‘strongly’ disagreed one made the point that existing mechanisms and codes of conduct should be improved and strengthened but on the other hand stressed the need for establishing policies promoting research integrity.

Taken the individual comments into consideration, a clear support of establishing additional mechanisms to support research integrity can be derived. Two approaches were suggested, a) developing high level agreements/minimum standards/framework/ethical principles within EOOSC and b) rely on existing mechanisms but extend or adapt if necessary. Two further points emerged from this answer pattern: there is certainly a need to define and standardize the use of terms (code of conduct, principles, framework, etc.) and to be precise in what is talked about; second, it is essential to first assess and evaluate what is already existing and then to derive where ethical support is needed.

Q6 Supporting research integrity #2

In figure 6 the distribution of answers to question 6 is presented:

Figure 6: *Q6: Research integrity can also be supported by enforcing comprehensive metadata policies, so that the full provenance and status of data and documents is known. Should EOOSC work towards a uniform application of comprehensive provenance metadata?*

Similar to question 5 a majority of participants (n=21) supported the view that the EOOSC should work towards a uniform application of metadata standards. For this question there was a similar distribution of those who strongly or partially agreed (12/9). Again four participants disagreed but only two of them strongly; one answer was missing

In the ‘strong’ agreement group (n=12), nine participants made clear statements that this is important, useful, a must, crucial, needed and a responsibility of the EOOSC but also a challenging issue (n=2). One participant proposed an EOOSC stamp of approval.

Those who partially agreed (n=9), raised some issues. Four participants had difficulties with the understanding of the question and/or the term ‘uniform’ in relation to application of metadata standards. It was argued that a uniform application of metadata standards will not work, given specific

materials, data and situations at hand (n=2). One participant gave a warning not to build up too much hurdles. There were four more positive statements. One participant agreed provided that sensitive personal data are adequately protected, another argued that the EOSC could have a role, a third one that enforcing metadata policies is a responsibility of the EOSC and another that harmonization should be sought at the level of cooperation.

From those who disagreed partially with this question (n=2), one referred to existing provenance solutions that can be used, the others recommended to be careful not to hinder innovation and to be prepared to update metadata policies if necessary.

One of the two participants who strongly disagreed made a clear statement not to go beyond what is minimally required to reach a goal, the other stated that not all research integrity issues could be solved by provenance metadata.

Despite high agreement that EOSC should work towards a uniform application of metadata standards and strong support by many participants, the answer pattern raises some issues. The formulation of the question was not clear to all participants and challenges with respect to implementation were seen by several participants. The result indicates a clear need to look at the issue of provenance metadata again and to work out more clearly what is proposed.

2. Use of data, personal and sensitive data

Q7 Unintended consequences of data use

Figure 7 summarizes the answers to question 7:

Figure 7: *Q7: The nature of a large federated set of data repositories, such as EOSC, means that data and other materials may be combined in unpredicted ways to generate unforeseen results. Should EOSC monitor and manage this type of data aggregation, so far as it can, and even restrict it in some cases?*

No clear answer pattern with respect to monitoring and managing data aggregation to prevent unforeseen results was observed: 18 participants agreed, 8 disagreed. Only 5 participants were 'strongly' in favour of this proposal and two strongly disagreed.

From the subgroup of participants that strongly agreed (n=5), three saw a primary responsibility more with partners of EOSC (tool developers, institutional responsibility, researchers) and one with EOSC itself. One participant stated that unforeseen results should be definitely monitored and reported.

In the largest subgroup of those who partially agreed (n=13), monitoring was recommended by four participants (one recommended even a service layer, one transparency about algorithms used) and establishment of a task force/committee by two. Another participant attested EOSC should become a leading example in ensuring that data linkage is done in protecting the privacy of the individual. One participant raised the importance of this issue for social surveys, two others pointed to possible positive effects of data linkage.

Four out of 6 participants who ‘partially’ disagreed were referring to possible positive effects of unforeseen results in research as long as they comply with basic ethical principles. One participant saw the issue as impractical, another argued that monitoring should not hinder research.

The two participants who strongly disagreed, stated that EOSC should not place itself into either a judge or a policeman or even stifle science.

Several participants were not happy with the formulation and direction of the question. Unforeseen results were seen primarily as a positive element in research provided that ethical principles are taken into consideration; it was felt that the primary responsibility is with EOSC partners rather than with the EOSC itself. There may be, however, a role for monitoring of unforeseen results in EOSC as stated by a substantial minority.

Q8. Sensitive personal data

In Figure 8 the answers to question 8 are displayed:

Figure 8: *Q8: The use of sensitive personal data is covered by principles of ethical research involving human subjects, and various pieces of legislation. Should EOSC try to introduce uniform policies with respect to the collection, storage, access and re-use of sensitive personal data (and the monitoring of that activity) within its constituent systems?*

The majority of participants (n=20) was in favour that EOSC should try to introduce uniform policies with respect to the collection, storage, access and re-use of sensitive personal data. From the five who answered 'no', three disagreed strongly. One answer was missing.

The following reasons were given for strong agreement (n=12): a need for harmonisation in EOSC (standards, alignment, shared policy, harmonisation; n=8), one participant stated that personal data requires particular care, one referred to GDPR, one argued that open and big data poses new challenges and another referred again to social surveys.

From those who partially agreed (n=8), three referred to existing legal and ethical frameworks (e.g. GDPR) and two saw more a facilitator role. One participant stated that this should be enforced by domain services, one required flexibility and the involvement of patient representatives and one stated that personal data requires particular care.

The reasons given for the three 'partial' disagreements were: no additional principles should be developed on top of legislation and domain-wise principles; better to leave it to existing organisations and not to allow information/data on the EOSC if there is no permission.

Two participants strongly opposed with reference to the existing GDPR.

Despite the fact that the majority agreed with this question, some criticism was raised. Only a minority saw a need for harmonisation in EOSC and a substantial subgroup referred to existing regulations.

3. The role of working groups and Ethics and Legal Advisory Board

Q9. The role of working groups

Figure 9 summarizes the answers to question 9:

Figure 9: Q9: Do you think that establishing theme or discipline specific, time-limited expert groups within the EOSC, to consider specific ethical / legal issues and propose relevant policies, would be a useful approach?

Here the answer pattern was quite uniform. All participants but one that answered this question were in favour of time-limited expert working groups within the EOSC to consider specific legal and ethical issues and to propose relevant policies.

Those who strongly agreed (n=14), gave the following reasons: essential, useful, efficient and reasonable approach, well working and representing an added value (n=9). One stated that it should be attempted but needs proper organisation, one that it might be a good strategy to identify new possible ethical problems and one stated that many ethical issues are content-sensitive with high variety across disciplines.

Reasons for partial agreement (n=8) were: limited to be conducted as needed, depending on the issues, relying on existing organisations, depending on the mandate of the groups, time and costs, need for an oversight body (which is part of the EOSCpilot recommendations), discipline-specific ethical impacts, and the need for patient representativeness.

The participant who expressed a partial disagreement considered this is issue as under disciplines' responsibility and not directly under the EOSC's.

All in all, support for theme or discipline specific time limited expert groups in the EOSC was overwhelming. Several proposals how the work of these groups could be optimised were made and should be taken into consideration if these groups are implemented.

Q10. An Ethics and Legal Advisory Board #1

The distribution of answers to question 10 is shown in figure 10:

Figure 10: Q10: Do you support the concept of an EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board, (within the EOSC governance structures, but independent of the EOSC executive) co-ordinating ethics related work (e.g. by identifying issues and setting up working groups)?

Here the majority 'strongly' agreed (n=19) and five more just 'partially'. Only two participants 'partially' disagreed and no one strongly.

Reasons given by the ‘strongly’ agreeing participants were: important (n=2), useful (n=2), needed, support for EOSC, necessary, reasonable, efficient mechanism, essential to safeguard data, mechanism for reviewing potential issues and ensure data integrity also across disciplines, fundamental to support public confidence. Three participants stressed the point of independence of the board, one asked for the composition of the board and another one specified coordination of the working groups and setting up a strategy for ensuring ethical practices as functionalities of the board.

Those who ‘partially’ agreed (n=5) required limitation of focus on needs, board only consulted when necessary and not as part of a complex management structure and dependence on the mandate of the group; one participant pointed out that if it is an advisory board, it should not have a coordinating role.

One participant expressed scepticism from the perspective of practicality (what is the scope, jurisdiction, etc.). Another questioned how decisions made by the board would be considered by the EOSC executive board.

In summary, there was overwhelming agreement with the concept of an independent EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board. Practical issues were raised over the composition and mandate of the board and the relation between the board and the EOSC management structure.

Q11 A Ethics and Legal Advisory Board #2

Figure 11 is presenting the distribution of answers to question 11:

Figure 11: *Q11: Do you support the idea of an EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board carrying out a periodic assessment of EOSC activities, from the point of view of ethical and legal compliance, and making that report public?*

The majority of participants (n=23) were in favour of a periodic assessment of the EOSC activities by the Ethics and Legal Advisory Board. Three disagreed with such a task for the board, two of them strongly.

Those who ‘strongly’ agreed (n=14) saw public reports as essential (n=3), advocated such reports to assess the impact and societal contribution of EOSC and to provide substantive support to build a positive societal image and public trust. In addition, such reports were seen as important for transparency and perceived as good to monitor EOSC (n=2). One participant stated that self-assessment and transparency are important activities to ensure compliance to ethical principles.

From the participants who agreed only ‘partially’ (n=9), three stressed the point that the report should be public. Three others were more critical: one saw parallels with a Data Protection Officer, another favoured peer reporting instead of a board and a third recommended that the board should work on demand.

The participant who ‘partially’ disagreed argued about the purpose of the advisory board. The remark was that such boards are not set up as bodies representing public interest and if that is required, better solutions should be proposed.

From the two participants that strongly disagreed, one questioned the necessity of monitoring if legal compliance is guaranteed beforehand and the other classified it as overhead.

In summary, there was an agreement by the majority of participants that a periodic assessment of EOSC activities from the viewpoint of legal and ethical compliance makes sense and that the report should be public; however, a substantial subgroup raised diverse concerns.

4. Training, Science and society, other issues

Q12 Ethics related training

Figure 12 summarizes the answers to question 12:

Figure 12: Q12: Do you believe EOSC should support training material and programmes about ethics and specific ethical issues, for researchers and infrastructure managers?

The majority of participants answered ‘yes’ (n=20). Only two participants disagreed. Three participants answered ‘I don’t know’ and from one participant the answer was missing.

Although optional, several participants added comments. One participant saw the necessity for a high level of awareness and understanding of ethical issues, two questioned that researchers are able to appreciate ethical implications and one reported positive effects of education in this area. Seven participants made specific proposals for topics of ethics related training, which could be used as useful input, if such a training is foreseen in EOSC. Two participants recommended to provide reference material and resources.

The participant who disagreed recommended to feed in the material about ethics into existing resources.

A last comment stated that such material should only be developed within EOSC if there is a shortage.

Clearly, a need for ethics related training material and programmes within EOSC was expressed by the overwhelming majority of participants of the survey. This was supplemented by a listing of topics to be covered in training activities.

Q13 Science and society

In figure 13 the answers to question 13 are summarized:

Figure 13: *Q13: Should EOSC play an active role in wider debates promoting the interpretation of accurate scientific knowledge in society?*

Whether EOSC should play an active role in wider debates promoting the interpretation of accurate scientific knowledge in society revealed no clear answer pattern. The majority answered positively (n=13) but there were seven 'no' and six 'I don't know' answers.

Two participants recommended a national and/or European public campaign, one a participation in science and society events and one a privileged and customised access for scientific journalists to success stories. Two other participants saw an inherent responsibility of the EOSC in this area, in order to make sure the society is correctly informed.

From those who disagreed (n=7), there were two statements, one to feed it into existing resources and one to postpone it to a later stage of the project. A third one suggested that others should do it, without specifying who.

Only around half of the participants agreed that EOSC should play an active role with respect to activities towards science and society. Maybe such activities can be postponed to later phases of the project, when EOSC is established and a critical mass of positive results is available.

Q14 Any Other issues

‘Are there particular ethics related issues that you feel have *not* been addressed, or not sufficiently addressed, by the current proposals and white paper?’

A considerable group (n=8) brought up additional ethical issues to be discussed, as follows:

- Address more detailed ethical issues about the cloud
- Ethics should reflect proper academic behaviour not religious restrictions
- Collaboration with commercial partners and how this affects research integrity
- Ethical issues intertwined with good science
- More emphasis on sustainable and responsible use of energy
- More recommendations about organisational ethics
- Promoting the important role of software in addition to data
- Transparency

4.3 Results according to stakeholder group

The 26 participants of the survey were recruited from 8 stakeholder groups. The largest subgroup consisted of RPOs, academic institutions or research libraries (RPO+) (n=12). In a descriptive analysis we compared this subgroup with the rest (n=14). Due to the small sample size no definitive conclusions could be drawn, however, the analysis revealed a few interesting differences.

RPO+ agreed with supporting organisational ethics and dealing with unintended consequences more often than the rest of participants, whereas the group ‘other’ was more often in favour of playing an active role in science and society. Supporting organisational ethics (Q4) was agreed by 7/12 participants from RPO+ compared to 7/14 from the rest. Unintended consequences of data (Q7) were seen as an issue to be considered in the EOSC by 10/12 of RPO+ but only from 8/14 of the other stakeholder groups. For 3/12 participants from the RPO+ group, EOSC should play an active role with respect to science and society (Q13) compared to 10/14 from the rest. 5/12 from the group RPO+ brought up other issues to be considered compared to 3/14 in the group ‘other’.

5. Discussion

There are three advisory bodies of the EC Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP), FAIR Data Expert Group and the EOSC High Level Expert Group (HLEG) (3). The OSPP paints the broader picture of Open Science as a goal and gives advice to the Commission encompassing dimensions, such as reward systems, measuring quality and impact, changing business models, citizen science and open education and skills. The FAIR Data Expert Group looks closely at the FAIR data principles and formulates recommendations how to implement them. Finally, the HLEG EOSC is expected to make recommendations on how to shape and implement the EOSC as a federated infrastructure for data-driven research, based on open standards and best practices.

In the interim report of HLEG (3), statements about data protection issues (e.g. GDPR, privacy sensitive concerns) and FAIR data principles are included. There are no direct references to ethical aspects, however, a need for trustworthiness and trusted environment is expressed. This is similar in the HLEG

recommendations by Muscella (4), where privacy and FAIR are mentioned and again references to trust, trustworthiness, trustable ecosystem and trusted repositories are made. Interestingly WGs and other advisory structures for the EOSC Executive Board are recommended without taking ethical aspects into consideration. The FAIR Data Action Plan (5) also refers to trustworthiness and trusted digital repositories without mentioning any association with ethics. There is clearly an interrelationship of governance, trust and ethics (6) and if trust or trustworthiness is seen as a definite need for the EOSC, it has to be specified how trust can be generated and maintained in the EOSC and how the ethics recommendations can support this process.

The only document, which clearly refers to ethical aspects are the Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations (7). Apart from confidentiality and issues around trust (public trust, trust and confidence, trusted repository), there is a specific section on research integrity. It is recommended that research integrity has to be assured (including the social, ethical and legal implications). All research organisations must have a research integrity policy, including promotion of good research practices, clear procedures dealing with allegations of research misconduct and a description of possible sanctions for proven cases of misconduct. All researchers must receive regular training and accreditation on research integrity pertaining to Open Science, including the ethical, legal and social implications of their research practices. The issue of research integrity is explicitly tackled in the ethics recommendations within the EOSCpilot project.

How the implementation and maintenance of trust and trustworthiness can be supported by the EOSCpilot ethics recommendations has to be explored further and has been discussed during a workshop held in Paris on 9 November, 2018.

6. References

1. EOSCpilot: Del 3.3 Draft Policy Recommendations (https://eoscpilot.eu/sites/default/files/eoscpilot_d3.3_final-withannexes-forweb.pdf)
2. EUSurvey: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>
3. Plasencia et al.: Prompting an EOSC in practice. Interim report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group (2017-2018) on the EOSC. Draft, June 2018 (https://www.eudat.eu/sites/default/files/prompting_an_eosc_in_practice_eosc_hleg_interim_report.pdf)
4. Muscella: Draft HLEG recommendations shared with the WP3 team on 17 October 2018; final version due to be published on 23 November 2018.
5. Collins et al.: FAIR Data Action Plan. Interim recommendations and actions from the European Commission. Expert Group on FAIR data. June 2018 (<https://zenodo.org/record/1285290#.W-LuJdEm7cs>)
6. Müller et al.: The interrelationship of governance, trust and ethics in temporary organisations. Decision making, Ethics, Governance, 2018
7. Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations, 22 April 2018 (https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/integrated_advice_opspp_recommendations.pdf)

7. Appendix

- 7.1 Survey questionnaire

EOSCpilot Wp3 Draft Policy Recommendations - Ethics

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

The EOSCpilot project has recently published [draft policy recommendations](#) as a step towards establishing the required policy environment to support the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). We are seeking feedback to formulate a set of final policy recommendations due for publication in December 2018.

This survey regards specifically the support and promotion of ethical behaviour within EOSC, discussed in a [White Paper](#) where potential ethical issues and related recommendations are presented. The paper can be resumed as follows:

The inclusion of ethical principles and policies are of fundamental importance to the EOSC, but it is difficult to anticipate all the ethical issues that may emerge as the scientific, technical, social and political landscape evolves. It is therefore crucial to have governance mechanisms in place that can ensure ethical issues are appropriately dealt with in the future, irrespective of how and when they occur, as well as identifying and proposing responses to current issues.

The complexity and diversity of potential issues requires an analysis of ethical issues relating to organisational conduct and policies, research conduct, research decision making, the use of data - especially sensitive data- and the interaction between science and society.

Because of this complexity, the paper proposes that ethical issues can be managed at a variety of different 'layers' of involvement and commitment. It proposes that as a minimum:

- *EOSC as an organisation should commit to act, and be seen to act, in an ethical manner, with policies and processes that reflect that commitment.*
- *EOSC should have structural mechanisms in place to support research integrity, for instance by establishing metadata systems that ensure accurate provenance data and appropriate acknowledgement of previous work.*

Many other issues will need specialist ethical (and often legal) expertise, in time limited working groups, to

propose specific policy responses.

The paper's authors strongly support the use of such groups, but also strongly recommend the establishment of a coordinating body, an Ethical and Legal Advisory Board, to oversee the work of specialist working groups, and to monitor and report on the ethical practice of the organisation.

Such a board would be distinct from the EOSC executive and be drawn from ethical and legal experts from stakeholder communities.

The paper's authors believe EOSC also has an important role to play in raising awareness about ethical issues within scientific communities, as well as in wider ethical debates, for instance around the interplay of scientific knowledge and society. Such input could be introduced as the EOSC itself matures, and the level of available resources becomes clearer.

The aim of the survey is to collect feedback on these proposals from different key stakeholder groups, such as funders and ministries, research infrastructures (RIs), and research producing organisations (RPOs), plus explore how the recommendations above can be integrated into the 'policy supporting services' that now need to be developed.

* The data collected will be sent to the EC's survey tool EUSurvey. The privacy statement of EU survey is here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/privacystatement>

Do you agree to take part in this survey sent to you by the EOSCpilot project? The data collected will be used to provide feedback on the policy recommendations. Access to the data will be restricted to members of the EOSCpilot project team. The data will be deleted at the end of the EOSCpilot project, or on request by you.

- Yes
 No

* I agree to provide my personal details for the participation in this survey.

- Yes (continue to provide details)
 No (continue anonymously)

Please provide contact details to allow us to follow up on any points of interest raised in your reply to this questionnaire

Name

Affiliation (Organisation you work for)

Job title

Country you are based

Email

* Which EOSC stakeholder category/ies do you consider yourself a member of? (if you belong to more than one, please choose the one you are representing when filling this survey)

at most 1 choice(s)

- Research Producing Organisations, Academic Institutions or Research Libraries
- Government ministries or agencies
- Service providers
- E-infrastructures, VREs or other pertinent H2020 projects
- Research funding bodies
- Research Infrastructures
- Enterprises
- Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations
- General public

Other category than specified above

* 1. What is your ethics background (please tick what fits best) ?

- ethics is one of my main professional activities
- my professional work has some associations with ethics
- I'm not working in this field but I'm interested in ethical questions
- other

Please specify

2. Would you characterise yourself as ethics expert ?

- Yes
- No

3. The importance of ethical issues

The recommendations on ethics are based on the assumption that supporting and promoting an ethical behaviour is of central importance to EOSC and should be explicitly built into the organisation from the outset. Do you agree with this assumption?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

4. Supporting organisational ethics

EOSC will be a federation of different organisations, each with their own ethical practices and obligations, reflecting their own regulatory environments and the activities in which they are engaged. Do you think that this will be sufficient to ensure that EOSC, as a whole, acts as an 'ethical organisation'?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

5. Supporting research integrity #1

Research integrity (ethical principles relating to the good practice of the individual researcher) is currently supported by research review mechanisms and codes of conduct. Should EOSC establish additional review mechanisms and codes of conduct relating to the use of EOSC resources?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

6. Supporting research integrity #2

Research integrity can also be supported by enforcing comprehensive metadata policies, so that the full provenance and status of data and documents is known. Should EOSC work towards a uniform application of comprehensive provenance metadata?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

7. Unintended consequences of data use

The nature of a large federated set of data repositories, such as EOSC, means that data and other materials may be combined in unpredicted ways to generate unforeseen results. Should EOSC monitor and manage this type of data aggregation, so far as it can, and even restrict it in some cases?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

8. Sensitive personal data

The use of sensitive personal data is covered by principles of ethical research involving human subjects, and various pieces of legislation. Should EOSC try to introduce uniform policies with respect to the collection, storage, access and re-use of sensitive personal data (and the monitoring of that activity) within its constituent systems?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

* Please give reasons for your answers

9. The role of working groups

Do you think that establishing theme or discipline specific, time-limited expert groups within the EOSC, to consider specific ethical / legal issues and propose relevant policies, would be a useful approach?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

*Please give reasons for your answers

10. An Ethics and Legal Advisory Board #1

Do you support the concept of an EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board, (within the EOSC governance structures, but independent of the EOSC executive) co-ordinating ethics related work (e.g. by identifying issues and setting up working groups)?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

*Please give reasons for your answers

11. An Ethics and Legal Advisory Board #2

Do you support the idea of an EOSC Ethics and Legal Advisory Board carrying out a periodic assessment of EOSC activities, from the point of view of ethical and legal compliance, and making that report public?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, partially
- No, strongly
- No, partially

*Please give reasons for your answers

12. Ethics related training

Do you believe EOSC should support training material and programmes about ethics and specific ethical issues, for researchers and infrastructure managers?

at most 1 choice(s)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, are there any specific topics you would like to see covered?

13. Science and society

Should EOSC play an active role in wider debates promoting the interpretation of accurate scientific knowledge in society?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please provide further details of the type of EOSC involvement you would like to see

14. Any Other issues

Are there particular ethics related issues that you feel have not been addressed, or not sufficiently addressed, by the current proposals and white paper?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please provide further details